

Childlessness in Context: Unpacking the Cultural Significance and Societal Pressures on Married Couples

Mina Margaret Ogbanga, PhD

Abstract

The study examined the cultural impact of childlessness on married couples in the society. An objective and one research question were raised for the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A population of 160,301 women in 65 communities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State was used. A sample of 100 women from 5 communities was used and this was done via multi-stage sampling technique of Random sampling technique and Proportionate sampling technique. The questionnaire titled "Socio-cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples Questionnaire (SICMCQ)" was used as instrument to collect relevant data. The instrument was validated by some experts and its reliability was tested for to be 0.75. The data collected, were analyzed using frequency, mean and percentage for the research question and Chi-square was used to test for the hypothesis. The findings from the study showed that childlessness brings about a high level of negative cultural impacts on married couples in diverse ways with mean ($\bar{x} = 3.18$). it was recommended among other things that measures should be directed towards the enhancement of medical facilities in the aide to curb the prevalence of childlessness in the society.

Introduction

Childlessness of married couples is worthy of note in the society as there is a norm guarding the perceptive view of individuals in the society as regards to this. The perception that is being directed towards childlessness of married couples has a long way of determining the rate at which they can find workable solutions to it. If these perceptive views are not properly handled, they can therefore bring about unnecessary stress, which have sometimes led to the dissolving of such union prone with this. While others are being able to handle whatever tantrums being thrown at them, there are some that are incapable of doing same. The extent of socio-cultural impact of childlessness among married couples is then noteworthy of being studied so as to help navigate the mind of people into the proper perspective on this subject matter. Childlessness questions the core of someone's being at the level of sexuality, the marital/life partner, and the ability to impart life to this life, to conceive and care for the next generation. It is associated with the loss of identity and a shattered sense of belonging. It also cuts off someone's hereditary hope (and birthright) because they are denied leaving their genetic footprint on this world after death. Several studies have confirmed that childlessness is

associated with emotional responses such as depression, anxiety, guilt, social isolation, and decreased self-esteem in both men and women (Cui, Wang & Wang, 2021 & Musa, Ramli, Yazmie, *et al.*, 2014). Although the association between childlessness and these emotional disturbances has been shown, there has been little research examining the specific nature of these variables in relation to childlessness

Childlessness refers to a person's biological inability to become pregnant after a year of regularly engaging in unprotected sexual activities. This is also known as the inability of an active, non-contraceptive couple to have a baby. It can either be primary or secondary: primary childlessness occurs in couples who have never been pregnant before, while secondary childlessness happens when pregnancy has failed following a previous one. Using the female's capability of conceiving as a way to distinguish between primary and secondary childlessness is, however, problematic, as it puts the blame of being childless on the woman's shoulders. (Stearns, 2010). *Ianna Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, Volume 5, Number 1 June, 2023 26

The World Health Organization (WHO) promotes the epidemiological view of what they term as "childlessness", which is the lack of conception within two years of exposure to pregnancy when infertility is not present (as mentioned in Ben, 2013). Sadly, those thought to be childless tend to be looked down upon and labeled with many negative terms. Thus, clinicians and epidemiologists use this term to refer to the struggles with both female and male fertility. Demographers define childlessness as the inability of a non-contraceptive, sexually active woman to have a live birth after at least one year of attempting to achieve a pregnancy (Joshi *et al.*, 2010). After a year of unprotected sexual intercourse without a resulting pregnancy, childlessness is defined as an inability to achieve such. This is commonly described as: no conception after one year of unprotected sexual activity. Having a child appears to be complexly motivated; driven by psychological needs, biological impulses and societal and historical customs.

Aim and Objective of the Study

Examine the social perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society.

Research Question

What are the social perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses are formulated for the study:

H0₁: There is no significant impact of social perception of childlessness on married couples in the society.

Significance of the Study

To married couples; the findings from this study will aid in the direction of the perception of married couples on the right track towards childlessness and enable them to develop an edge towards seeking for solutions without being stressed.

Scope of the Study

This study will strictly focus on examining socio-cultural and childlessness impact on married couples in the society. The target population for this study will comprise of married couples in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Definition of Terms

Childlessness: This refers to the inability of procuring an offspring.

Impact: This refers to the exacerbated influence an entity has on another.

Socio-Cultural Impact: This refers to the influence exerted by the society on another entity socially and culturally.

Married Couples: These are individuals that have decided to imbibe the duty of coming together to live as one legally, traditionally or religiously.

Cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples in the Society

The African tradition places a lot of importance on the possession of children particularly male children. 'Places' is used above because this tradition has not changed much even in the face of the exploits of modernity in Africa. In the cultural setting of most African communities, Nigeria inclusive, as a result of the lack of life assurance policies or a social security system put in place to cater for the aged, there is the need to have one's own children who would look after them in old age or celebrate them when they are no more (Mudiare, 2013). In Africa the prime responsibility of the woman to her husband is that of bearing children especially a male heir. In most societies, the upbringing of a woman is geared towards making her a viable product for marriage and once married; the social pressure to become pregnant is great. In modern society especially western societies, children are often described as "making a family" (HasmanováMarhánková, 2015). Married couples that are blessed with the gift of children are often seen as constituting a proper natural and complete family while the childless couple is seen as excluded from the joys of family life. The traditional value for procreation has always been a major cause of many family upheavals. Infertility represent a potentially serious source of conflict, quarrels, dissention and other forms of maladjustment in many Nigeria homes regardless of their educational attainment and socio-economic status.

It is common within traditional African settings that the inability to make babies in a marriage is often blamed on the woman, as such the society exhibits some kind of bias against women which leads to a kind of stereotyping. This is often a cultural thing which has to do with values of a people that has been acquired overtime, and influenced by both internal and external factors (Mbachaga&Akaa, 2015). This position is what informs the basis for most of what looks like stereotypical images of women in most African societies. Stereotypical impressions come with the attendant problems of prejudice and misrepresentations thus introducing a strain on the various levels of relationships between spouses, genders or the family unit. This issue of the

quest and obsession for children has become phenomenal in all African societies despite the attendant socioeconomic problems occasioned by the persistence of high fertility especially in third world countries. The disregard for the harsh economic conditions that is birthed by large number of children in families in parts of Nigeria as manifestation of the great value placed on children is the extreme fanfare that characterizes the arrival of a child into a family (Ishola, Owolabi & Filippi, 2017). The structure and the unifying function of the family which can be seen as an umbilical cord that bilaterally links the interactional activities in a given society thus places it as the most crucial unit of all human organizations, hence its continuity and progress through procreation connotes harmony while its disruption leads to a number of social problems ranging from divorce, prostitution, betrayal, violence, etc.

Methodology

Research Design

The design of this study is the descriptive research design. This design is that which employs both qualitative and quantitative data for the proper dissemination of the stated questions that are formulated to dissolve the major purpose for this study. This research design was chosen because of the purpose of the study to gather information on socio-cultural impact of childlessness on married couples in the society.

Population of the Study

The population for this study will comprise of women present in the 65 communities in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, which constitutes to a total estimation of 160,301 women (National Population Census, (2008) and World Sex Ratio (2021)).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique of random sampling technique and proportionate sampling technique will be used for sample selection. Random sampling technique will be used in the

selection of 5 communities out of the 65 communities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State. Proportionate sampling technique will then be adopted in the selection of 20 women each in the chosen communities. A total sample of 100 women will then be given and used for the study, as stipulated in the table below:

Table 1: Sample Distribution

S/N	Districts	Sample Chosen
1	Choba	20
2	Rumueme	20
3	Ozuoba	20
4	Rumuokoro	20
5	Rumuigbo	20
Total		100

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument employed in this study is the questionnaire. It is a 20-item self-structure instrument titled “**Socio-cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples Questionnaire (SICMCQ)**” that will be partitioned into two sections (A and B). Section A will cover the demographic aspect of it, which collects personal information about the respondents, while section B will cover the items, which elicited the responses of the respondents on each of the item statements present. The items are responded to with the aid of 4-point Likert scale of measurement of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Method of Data Collection

Data will be collected using questionnaires. The researcher will go to the field and meet up with respondents, then hand out the copies of the questionnaire to them. These respondents will be given directives on how to go about the filling of the distributed instrument. After completion, the researcher will proceed to retrieve the distributed instrument immediately.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

Face and content validity of the instrument will be established by giving it to my supervisor and two other lecturers in the Department of Sociology. Their inputs will be ratified further by the supervisor, before its incorporation in the production the final draft of the questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument will be done through the test-retest method. This method is that which involves the administration of the instrument to a selected group of 20 women (outside the sample of the study but within the population of the study) with a separating time difference of 10 days between the two administrations. The responses gotten from the two administrations will then be compared and correlated through the adoption of Pearson Product Moment Correlation, so as to arrive at the reliability co-efficient index of 0.75.

Method of Data Analysis

The data will be subjected to an analytical procedure with the aid of frequency, mean and percentage for the research questions. Chi-square will be used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The criterion-mean will be calculated for as follows:

- Strongly Agree (SA) - 4points
- Agree (A) - 3points
- Disagree (D) - 2points
- Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1point

$$\text{Criterion mean} = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$$

The item with a mean score that is up to and above the criterion mean will be “accepted” while the one with a mean score that is below the criterion mean will be “rejected”.

Results and Discussion

Results

Demographic Analysis

Table 1: Frequency and percentage of the demographics of women

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
20-29yrs	30	30%
30-39yrs	45	45%
40-49yrs	25	25%
50yrs & above	0	0%
Marital Status		
Single	25	25%
Married	55	55%
Divorced	15	15%
Widowed	5	5%
Separated	0	0%

From the analysis done above, it was displayed that 30% of the total sampled women are of 20-29yrs, 45% of the total sampled women are of 30-39yrs, 25% of the total sampled women are of 40-49yrs; 25% of the total sampled women are single, 55% of the total sampled women

are married, 15% of the total sampled women are divorced while 5% of the total sampled women are widowed.

Research Question: What is the cultural impact of childlessness on married couples in the society?

Table 2: Mean statistics displaying the cultural impact of childlessness on married couples in the society

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Remark
13	Childlessness brings about less form of acceptability in the African society.	30 (120)	40 (120)	20 (40)	10 (10)	2.9	Accepted
14	Childlessness brings about a desire to seek out diabolical help.	34 (136)	56 (168)	10 (20)	0 (0)	3.24	Accepted
15	Childlessness drives in the mind the feel of insufficiency in the family based on culture perceived.	35 (140)	65 (195)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.35	Accepted
16	Childlessness results to out-casting of heinous thoughts in the background of couples.	33 (132)	55 (165)	12 (24)	0 (0)	3.21	Accepted
Grand Mean						3.18	High

Data in the table above displayed the mean responses of the women on the cultural impact of childlessness on married couples in the society. From the analysis done, all the items with respective mean scores of 2.9, 3.24, 3.35 and 3.21 were accepted because their mean scores are above the criterion-mean score of 2.5. Based on the grand mean score obtained at 3.18, it can

therefore be deduced that childlessness brings about a high level of negative cultural impacts on married couples in diverse ways.

Discussion of Findings

On the cultural aspect, it was also revealed in analysis done in Tables 2 that there is a high level of negative cultural perception attributed to childlessness of married couples in the society and that childlessness brings about a high level of negative cultural impacts on married couples in diverse ways and that there is a significant impact of cultural perception of childlessness on married couples in the society. This was corroborated with the findings of Dierickx, Rahbari, Longman,*et al.* (2018) who ascertained that childlessness can be a traumatic and worrying experience for men and women who for cultural or personal reasons, view childbearing as central to their live.

Recommendations

- 1) Measures should be directed towards the enhancement of medical facilities in the aide to curb the prevalence of childlessness in the society.
- 2) This study contributed to knowledge as it has documented the socio-cultural impact of childlessness impact on married couples in the society.

References

- Anokye, R., Acheampong, E., Mprah, W. K., Ope, J. O. & Barivure, T. N. (2017). Psychosocial effects of infertility among couples attending St. Michael's Hospital, Jachie-Pramso in the Ashanti Region of Ghana. *BMC Research Notes*, 10(1), 1-5.
- Botwe, B. O., Bamfo-Quaicoe, K., Hunu, E. & Anim-Sampong, S. (2015). Hysterosalpingographic findings among Ghanaian women undergoing infertility work-up: a study at the Korle-Bu Teaching Hospital. *Fertility Research and Practice*, 1(1), 1-6.
- Cui, C., Wang, L. & Wang, X. (2021). Effects of self-esteem on the associations between infertility-related stress and psychological distress among infertile chinese women: a cross-sectional study. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 14, 1245.

- Dierickx, S., Rahbari, L., Longman, C., Jaiteh, F. & Coene, G. (2018). 'I am always crying on the inside': a qualitative study on the implications of infertility on women's lives in urban Gambia. *Reproductive Health*, 15(1), 1-11.
- Egharevba, O. J. (2020). The Socio-Cultural impact of Childlessness on Married Couples in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria. *FULafia Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(4), 50-65.
- Fehintola, A. O., Fehintola, F. O., Ogunlaja, O. A., Awotunde, T. O., Ogunlaja, I. P. & Onwudiegwu, U. (2017). Social meaning and consequences of infertility in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. *Sudan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 12(2), 63-77.
- Gouni, O., Jarašiūnaitė-Fedosejeva, G., Kömürçü Akik, B., Holopainen, A. & Calleja-Agius, J. (2022). Childlessness: Concept Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(3), 1464.
- Hasmanová Marhánková, J. (2015). The changing practices and meanings of grandparenthood. Reflections on the demographical trends and changing representations of ageing. *Sociology Compass*, 9(4), 309-319.
- Hollos, M. & Whitehouse, B. (2014). Women in limbo: life course consequences of infertility in a Nigerian community. *Human Fertility*, 17(3), 188-191.
- Ibisomi, L. & Mudege, N. N. (2014). Childlessness in Nigeria: perceptions and acceptability. *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 16(1), 61-75.
- Isah, B. A., Yahayah, M., Panti, A. A., Abubakar, S., Shehu, A., Bello, A. S. & Abdulaziz, M. D. (2018). Perceived causes of infertility and its psychosocial effects among women with infertility attending gynaecology clinic in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto. *IOSR Journal of Dentistry and Medical Sciences*, 17(11), 26-30.
- Ishola, F., Owolabi, O. & Filippi, V. (2017). Disrespect and abuse of women during childbirth in Nigeria: A systematic review. *PloS One*, 12(3), e0174084.
- Mbachaga, D. J. & Akaa, A. A. (2015). Infertility in marriage and its impact on the family: James Alachi's Your precious Ihotu. *Creative Artist: A Journal of Theatre and Media Studies*, 9(1), 66-83.
- Mudiare, P. E. U. (2013). Abuse of the aged in Nigeria: Elders also cry. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 3(9), 79-87.
- Musa, R., Ramli, R., Yazmie, A. W. A., Khadijah, M. B. S., Hayati, M. Y., Midin, M., ... & Ravindran, A. (2014). A preliminary study of the psychological differences in infertile couples and their relation to the coping styles. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 55, S65-S69.
- Mustafa, M., Sharifa, A. M., Hadi, J., Ilzam, E. & Aliya, S. (2019). Male and female infertility: causes, and management. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*, 18, 27-32.

- Nnadi, I. (2013). Son preference-A violation of women's human rights: A case study of Igbo custom in Nigeria. *Journal of Politics & Law*, 6, 134.
- Nwaomah, E. N. & Dube, S. (2018). Involuntary childlessness and its socio-cultural impact on married couples: Implications for pastoral counseling. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 3(10), 410-414.
- Obiyo, I. D. (2016). Impact of Childlessness on Marriage.(A study of married couples in Lowa community, Imo State). *International Journal of Religious and Cultural Practice*, 2(1), 9-17.
- Ogbanga, M. M., & Sharma, S. N. (2024). Climate Change and Mental Heat. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13284459>
- Ojedokun, I. M. (2019). Influence of family and spiritual supports on coping with infertility among couples in Ibadan Oyo State Nigeria. *African Journal for the Psychological Studies of Social Issues*, 22(3), 205-216.
- Okantey, G. N. O., Adomako, E. B., Baffour, F. D. & Lim, D. (2021). Sociocultural implications of infertility and challenges in accessing assisted reproductive technology: Experiences of couples from two health facilities in southern Ghana. *Marriage & Family Review*, 57(5), 375-396.
- Okin, S. M. (2015). Justice, gender, and the family. In *Justice, Politics, and the Family* (pp. 63-87). Routledge.
- Okpan, S. O. & Otega, O. (2021). Socio-cultural consequences of being childless; perspectives across Africa and Europe. *Nigerian Journal of Social Problems and Social Policy Review*, 1(2).
- Rasak, B. & Oladipo, P. (2017). Childlessness and its socio-cultural implication on married couples within some selected Yoruba communities in South-West Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 5(1), 42-54.
- Saumet, J., Petropanagos, A., Buzaglo, K., McMahon, E., Warraich, G. & Mahutte, N. (2018). No. 356-egg freezing for age-related fertility decline. *Journal of obstetrics and gynaecology Canada*, 40(3), 356-368.
- Schenk, J. L. (2018). Principles of maximizing bull semen production at genetic centers. *Animal*, 12(s1), s142-s147.
- Upadhyay, Y., Chhabra, A. & Nagar, J. C. (2020). A women infertility: an overview. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development*, 8(2), 99-106.

- Wando, O. A. (2017). *Knowledge, attitude and socio-cultural beliefs and practices among infertile persons in Kisumu County, Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, Moi University).
- Youens, D., Halkett, G., Wright, C., O'Connor, M., Schofield, P., Jefford, M., ... & RT Prepare project team. (2019). Assessing the cost-effectiveness of RT Prepare: A radiation therapist-delivered intervention for reducing psychological distress prior to radiotherapy. *Psycho-Oncology*, 28(5), 1110-1118.